

Activation of TRP Channels is involved in Ros-Dependent Regulation of Blood Flow by Astringent Polyphenols

*Taiki Fushimi ⁽¹⁾

(1) Graduate School of Engineering and Science, Shibaura Institute of Technology, Saitama, Saitama, Japan.

*Corresponding author: nb21110@shibaura-it.ac.jp

A recent large intervention study found that long-term consumption of the flavan-3-ol (FLs) fraction significantly reduced cardiovascular death, but the mechanisms are unclear because of its poor bioavailability. To address this issue, we investigated the redox properties, bioactivity and docking affinity into TRP channel of EC and its oligomers (procyanidin B2: dimer, procyanidin C1; trimer, or A2; tetramer).

Keywords: astringent polyphenols